

Radiation levels in the SPS during the 2015-2018 operation

Kacper Bilko, Ruben Garcia Alia
CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

Abstract

The Super Proton Synchrotron (SPS) is the second largest accelerator at CERN where protons (ions) are accelerated up to 450 GeV (177 GeV/u). Unavoidable beam losses, leading to the mixed-field radiation of up to MGy magnitude, pose a threat to reliability of the electronic equipment and polymer materials located in the tunnel and its vicinity. In addition to active monitors such as Beam Loss Monitors (BLM) or Radiation Monitors (RadMon), the SPS had been equipped with passive dosimeters, namely Radio-Photo-Luminescence (RPL) and NMOS transistors, allowing point-wise measurement of the Total Ionizing Dose (TID). With the variety of radiation monitors and dosimeters distributed across the Super Proton Synchrotron (SPS), this report aims to give a comprehensive picture of the radiation levels, primarily TID, in the years 2015-2018.

Keywords: BLM, total ionising dose, TID, SPS, NMOS, RadMon, HEH, intensity, RPL, TT20, TT40, TT41, transfer lines, Run 2

Contents

1	Introduction	4
1	SPS Layout	4
2	SPS injected intensities and operation statistics	5
3	Radiation Monitoring in the SPS	6
4	Description of the analysis procedure	9
5	How to use this report?	11
2	TID measurements in the SPS ring	12
1	Summary of the TID in the SPS in years 2014-2018.	12
2	LSS1	13
3	LSS2	15
4	LSS3	17
5	LSS4	19
6	LSS5	21
7	LSS6	23
8	ARC12	25
9	ARC23	27
10	ARC34	29
11	ARC45	31
12	ARC56	33
13	ARC61	35
14	Comparison of the ARC BLM measurements with RPLs and NMOS dosimeters	37
3	HEHeq fluence measurements in the SPS ring	38
4	TID measurements in the selected Transfer Lines	39
1	TT40 / TT41	39
2	TT20	40
5	Discussion and Conclusions	41
	Acknowledgement	42
	References	43
	Appendices A BLM vs RPL measurements for years 2014-2015 and 2017-2018	44
1	2014-2015	44
2	2017-2018	50
	Appendices B Injector Schedules	57
1	2014	58
2	2015	59
3	2016	60
4	2017	61
5	2018	62

Appendices C	BLM annual measurements	63
Appendices D	Choice of BCT	73
Appendices E	RadMon Annual Measurements	76

Chapter 1

Introduction

1 SPS Layout

The SPS is a circular accelerator of almost 7 km circumference, consisting of 6 sextants. Each sextant contains of Long Straight Section (LSS) and two arcs (Arc+ and Arc-), at the each side of the LSS. The accelerator is organised in 2×108 half-periods (determined by the main quadruple locations), each of approximately 52 m. Each sextant contains 2×18 half-periods – 2×4 attributed to LSS and 2×7 to each of the arcs. The schematic layout is depicted in Fig. 1.1.

Fig. 1.1: Schematic layout of the SPS. Credit: [1].

Assuming that X denotes the sextant’s number (1,..,6), the Arc-, LSS, Arc+ would span over half-periods X00-X13, X14-X21, X22-X35 respectively. In the scope of this report, the LHC arc naming convention will be applied, e.g. Arc12 consists of both arcs (Arc 1+, Arc 2-) between LSS1 and LSS2. In the SPS each component of the accelerator (e.g. magnet or beam instrumentation) is assigned with an element number (two digits), depending on the location within the half-period. To identify the location of an equipment, in addition to half-period, an element number is required, e.g. location 11208, corresponds to the 12th half-period in sextant 1, element 08 (which cannot be easily transformed to dcum, without information from the layout database).

The functionality of each LSS is listed below.

LSS1: hosts internal beam dump (used prior Run 3) and TT10 injection transfer line (PS to SPS),
 LSS2: is slow extraction region, with beam transferred towards North Area,
 LSS3: is a region of Radio Frequency cavities (beam's acceleration),
 LSS4: performs fast extraction towards LHC beam 1 or AWAKE experiment,
 LSS5: hosts beam instrumentation and UA9 experiment [2], and as of 2021, new internal beam dump,
 LSS6: conducts fast extraction towards LHC beam 2 or HiRadMat experiment.

2 SPS injected intensities and operation statistics

Based on the injector operation schedules, attached in Appendix B, the analysis was narrowed down to periods with the possibility of having a beam in the accelerator. Those periods, together with the corresponding integrated injected intensities, are listed in Tab. 1.1. Reduced injected intensity in 2016 is a consequence of a vacuum leak in the dump assembly [3].

Table 1.1: Considered periods with the corresponding injected intensities.

Year	Start	End	Proton Injected Intensity (1e19 p)	Ion Injected Intensity (1e15 charges)
2014	2014-09-11	2014-12-16	0.27	0.18
2015	2015-01-27	2015-12-15	1.81	17.04
2016	2016-03-14	2016-12-13	1.04	8.24
2017	2017-04-27	2017-12-19	1.49	8.36
2018	2018-03-16	2018-12-11	1.95	8.01

The evolution of the injected intensity (for protons and ions) accumulated over time is depicted in Fig. 1.2. Intensity analysis has been performed based on the information from 4 Beam Current Transformers, with the selection made according to Tab. D.1.

Fig. 1.2: Evolution of the injected intensity accumulated over time for proton and ion operations.

3 Radiation Monitoring in the SPS

Various types of radiation monitors are available in the SPS, namely:

- Beam Loss Monitors – relatively high time resolution of the TID measurements (integrated data for each SPS cycle), but not designed primarily as dosimeters,
- Radiation Monitors (RadMons) – measure quantities relevant in terms of radiation effects on electronics, with their time evolution.
- Radio-Photo-Luminescence (RPL) dosimeters – high dynamic range, however provide only cumulative TID measurement (with 1-2 year resolution, depending on the human intervention frequency),
- NMOS transistor based dosimeters – dosimeters designed to measure TID in the same way, as TID degrades electronic components (shift in the threshold voltage). The time resolution depends on the readout frequency (in this report annual data presented).

Fig. 1.3: Locations of the radiation monitors used in this report. In the typical half-period of an arc, BLM can be installed either at the beam height (around 30 cm from the beam axis), upstream of the defocusing quadrupole (*side BLM*), or under the beginning of the first dipole magnet in the half-period (*bottom BLM*, in the half-periods starting with focusing quadrupole).

Whereas in the LSSs the locations of the monitors aim to cover critical elements, hence involves additional sensors, in the arc half-periods the distribution of the detectors is periodic. Example of the

sensors installations are presented in Fig. 1.3 and Fig. 1.5.

3.1 Beam Loss Monitors

The beam loss monitoring system deployed in the SPS consists of ~ 270 monitors, ionisation chambers filled with nitrogen [reference needed]. Example of the monitor is presented in Fig. 1.4. The data provided by the system are the TID integrated over each SPS cycle, with the 1 bit (i.e. resolution) equal to 110 or 114 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{cycle}$ (for majority of monitors and cycles). In case of low dose areas such a resolution (and effective low signal to noise ratio) reduces the precision of the measurements. In 2018, roughly 1.1×10^6 cycles were identified as potentially involving beam in the machine. Assuming that a dose received by a BLM in each of those cycles was 56 μGy (almost the half of ADC resolution), the annual TID at that BLM would be $\sim 60 \text{ Gy}$, even though the measured one (neglecting the impact of the noise) would be equal to 0 Gy, due to rounding of the ADC conversion.

In the arc half-periods, two locations of a BLM are possible – i) upstream of the defocusing BLM, ii) below the beginning of the first dipole magnet in the half-period (Fig. 1.4), for half-periods starting with focusing quadrupole (example of such an installation in Fig. 1.3). As opposed to arc regions, distribution of the BLMs in each of the LSSs is unique, with additional monitors installed. In this document, BLMs that are installed side of the beam are denoted as side BLMs, rest of the BLMs (installed below beam plane) is referred as bottom BLMs.

An example of the measured TID for both an ARC and a LSS BLMs is depicted in Fig. 1.8

Fig. 1.4: Example of the Beam Loss Monitor installed in the arc half-period of the SPS.

3.2 RadMons

The RadMon system allows measuring the important quantities in terms of electronics damage. It consists of RadFETs (p-channel MosFETs), which measure TID, silicon p-i-n diodes for the measurement of the 1-MeV equivalent neutron fluence, and SRAM memories for the HEH and thermal neutron fluences' evaluations. In most of the locations, RadMons have been deployed in the vicinity of the arc quadrupole magnets, below the beam line. An example of the installation is depicted in Fig. 1.3. Annual measurements (that were available and had reasonable time-evolutions) of TID and HEHeq fluence are listed in Tab. E.1.

3.3 Radio-Photo-Luminescence dosimeters

The RPL dosimeter are made of silver activated metaphosphate glass [reference needed]. The ionizing radiation creates radio-photoluminescence centers, and after the exposition to UV light, luminescence intensity is measured. Since the calibration function is a multi-valued function, a complementary measurement of the light attenuation is performed, to determine the TID [add reference]. Locations of the RPL dosimeters in the arc regions are periodic, with one dosimeter installed at the cable tray and one at the quadrupole magnet coil in every half-period (example depicted in Fig. 1.5). In the LSSs, however, additional dosimeters have been installed, e.g. to measure TID at the dump blocks. Detailed description of the RPL locations can be found in [4].

Fig. 1.5: Locations of the RPL dosimeters in a half-period of the SPS Arc. Credit: HSE-RP-AS [4].

3.4 Passive NMOS

Around 190 passive NMOS transistors were installed along the SPS, allowing annual TID measurements, based on the shift in the threshold voltage [5]. Dosimeters were installed mostly in the arc regions, on top of the Beam Instrumentation group's racks, with the distance from the beam either 85 cm (for type-A racks) or 40 cm (for type-B racks) [6]. In this report measurements (presented in [6]) at both types of racks are considered together. An example of the dosimeter on the type-A rack is presented in Fig. 1.3.

4 Description of the analysis procedure

To cope with the lack of high-frequency dose rate data (logged over each SPS cycle, that would allow more accurate analysis), and low resolution of the BLM loss-per-cycle measurements (most of the dose accumulated over the first bits, as determined by ADC, especially important for low-dose regions), the following approach has been developed and applied:

1. Consider only beam run periods (Tab. 1.1).
2. Assign the beam's user for each cycle, based on the cycle name.
3. Analyse intensity evolution, cycle by cycle, using information from one out of 4 available Beam Current Transformers (preference described in Tab. D.1), to determine if beam has actually been in the SPS (example of the intensity traces in Fig. 1.6).
4. Split loss-per-cycle (integrated TID over the cycle) BLM measurements in the samples, with respect to the beam presence, to obtain two histograms: for beamIn and noBeam cycles.
5. For each BLM in each year, integrate the positive contribution of the $beamIn - k \cdot noBeam$ (where $k = \frac{fillsBeam}{fillsNoBeam}$ is a scaling factor) distribution to retrieve the annual TID measurement (example of this step depicted in Fig. 1.7).

Fig. 1.6: Examples of the intensity evolution over cycles

Fig. 1.7: Example of the BLM data processing (offset correction).

(a) a LSS BLM (half-period 221), TID over time

(b) a LSS BLM (half-period 221), TID over injected intensity

(c) an ARC BLM (half-period 235), TID over time

(d) an ARC BLM (half-period 235), TID over injected intensity

Fig. 1.8: An example of the TID evolution over time and injected intensity for selected ARC and LSS BLMs.

5 How to use this report?

The core of the report constitutes the plots of the annual TID distribution for selected radiation monitors across the SPS, presented in chapter 2. An example of such a plot is depicted in Fig. 1.9. Each plot contains 2 layout subplots – the lower presents selected magnets and beam instrumentation, whereas the upper illustrates radiation monitors/dosimeters. All figures are attached as a vector graphics, therefore after enlarging the layout, the element names can be traced.

Fig. 1.9: An example of the annual TID measurements in one of the SPS sectors, with the magnet and monitors/dosimeters layout.

In case of BLMs and RPL detectors, their dcum coordinates were not available, therefore they were assigned (with some level of uncertainty) according to pictures from the tunnel and layout drawings (for RPLs presented in [4]).

RPL measurements have not always been retrieved on the annual basis – in 2014–2018 period, 3 measurements were available: 2014 together with 2015, 2016, and 2017 combined with 2018. Therefore, in case of annual representations, the TID has been divided according to the proportion of injected intensity listed in Tab. 1.1. This is the approximation, that assumes that TID scaled with the injected intensity (might not be correct at all locations). Significant discrepancy between RPL and BLM measurement, that exist in only one of the years (out of two, with cumulative RPL measurement), would indicate that this approximation is not valid for a given region. Appendix A contains plots with BLM TID integrated over the same periods as for RPLs, and therefore not biased by the $TID \sim Intensity$ assumption.

The naming convention of the RPL dosimeters used in this report, visible in layout of the plots (*SEXTANT.(ARC|LSS).(COIL|CABLE).RPL_ID*), reflects the naming used in the HSE-RP annual reports [4], where measurements are divided by sextant, region (ARC/LSS) and location (cable/coil).

Chapter 2

TID measurements in the SPS ring

1 Summary of the TID in the SPS in years 2014-2018.

Fig. 2.1: Distribution of the TID measurements in the years: 2014-2015, 2016, and 2017-2018, represented as violin plots, for both Arcs and LSSs. Each type of radiation monitor, i.e. side BLM, bottom BLM (including BLMs in the LSS, located below the beam), NMOS (positions A and B considered together), RadMon (inc. deported modules), RPL at the magnet coil, and RPL at the wall/cable; has been plotted as a separate violin, with the width corresponding to the number of measurements for a given sector. Each violin, with sufficiently large number of measurements, contains 3 horizontal bars, at the values of first, second, and third quartile (25%, 50%, 75% measurements respectively below the value).

2 LSS1

2.1 2015

Fig. 2.2: Distribution of the TID in LSS1 during the 2015 operation.

2.2 2016

Fig. 2.3: Distribution of the TID in LSS1 during the 2016 operation.

2.3 2017

Fig. 2.4: Distribution of the TID in LSS1 during the 2017 operation.

2.4 2018

Fig. 2.5: Distribution of the TID in LSS1 during the 2018 operation.

3 LSS2

3.1 2015

Fig. 2.6: Distribution of the TID in LSS2 during the 2015 operation.

3.2 2016

Fig. 2.7: Distribution of the TID in LSS2 during the 2016 operation.

3.3 2017

Fig. 2.8: Distribution of the TID in LSS2 during the 2017 operation.

3.4 2018

Fig. 2.9: Distribution of the TID in LSS2 during the 2018 operation.

4 LSS3

4.1 2015

Fig. 2.10: Distribution of the TID in LSS3 during the 2015 operation.

4.2 2016

Fig. 2.11: Distribution of the TID in LSS3 during the 2016 operation.

4.3 2017

Fig. 2.12: Distribution of the TID in LSS3 during the 2017 operation.

4.4 2018

Fig. 2.13: Distribution of the TID in LSS3 during the 2018 operation.

5 LSS4

5.1 2015

Fig. 2.14: Distribution of the TID in LSS4 during the 2015 operation.

5.2 2016

Fig. 2.15: Distribution of the TID in LSS4 during the 2016 operation.

5.3 2017

Fig. 2.16: Distribution of the TID in LSS4 during the 2017 operation.

5.4 2018

Fig. 2.17: Distribution of the TID in LSS4 during the 2018 operation.

6 LSS5

6.1 2015

Fig. 2.18: Distribution of the TID in LSS5 during the 2015 operation.

6.2 2016

Fig. 2.19: Distribution of the TID in LSS5 during the 2016 operation.

6.3 2017

Fig. 2.20: Distribution of the TID in LSS5 during the 2017 operation.

6.4 2018

Fig. 2.21: Distribution of the TID in LSS5 during the 2018 operation.

7 LSS6

7.1 2015

Fig. 2.22: Distribution of the TID in LSS6 during the 2015 operation.

7.2 2016

Fig. 2.23: Distribution of the TID in LSS6 during the 2016 operation.

7.3 2017

Fig. 2.24: Distribution of the TID in LSS6 during the 2017 operation.

7.4 2018

Fig. 2.25: Distribution of the TID in LSS6 during the 2018 operation.

8 ARC12

8.1 2015

Fig. 2.26: Distribution of the TID in ARC12 during the 2015 operation.

8.2 2016

Fig. 2.27: Distribution of the TID in ARC12 during the 2016 operation.

8.3 2017

Fig. 2.28: Distribution of the TID in ARC12 during the 2017 operation.

8.4 2018

Fig. 2.29: Distribution of the TID in ARC12 during the 2018 operation.

9 ARC23

9.1 2015

Fig. 2.30: Distribution of the TID in ARC23 during the 2015 operation.

9.2 2016

Fig. 2.31: Distribution of the TID in ARC23 during the 2016 operation.

9.3 2017

Fig. 2.32: Distribution of the TID in ARC23 during the 2017 operation.

9.4 2018

Fig. 2.33: Distribution of the TID in ARC23 during the 2018 operation.

10 ARC34

10.1 2015

Fig. 2.34: Distribution of the TID in ARC34 during the 2015 operation.

10.2 2016

Fig. 2.35: Distribution of the TID in ARC34 during the 2016 operation.

10.3 2017

Fig. 2.36: Distribution of the TID in ARC34 during the 2017 operation.

10.4 2018

Fig. 2.37: Distribution of the TID in ARC34 during the 2018 operation.

11 ARC45

11.1 2015

Fig. 2.38: Distribution of the TID in ARC45 during the 2015 operation.

11.2 2016

Fig. 2.39: Distribution of the TID in ARC45 during the 2016 operation.

11.3 2017

Fig. 2.40: Distribution of the TID in ARC45 during the 2017 operation.

11.4 2018

Fig. 2.41: Distribution of the TID in ARC45 during the 2018 operation.

12 ARC56

12.1 2015

Fig. 2.42: Distribution of the TID in **ARC56** during the **2015** operation.

12.2 2016

Fig. 2.43: Distribution of the TID in **ARC56** during the **2016** operation.

12.3 2017

Fig. 2.44: Distribution of the TID in ARC56 during the 2017 operation.

12.4 2018

Fig. 2.45: Distribution of the TID in ARC56 during the 2018 operation.

13 ARC61

13.1 2015

Fig. 2.46: Distribution of the TID in ARC61 during the 2015 operation.

13.2 2016

Fig. 2.47: Distribution of the TID in ARC61 during the 2016 operation.

13.3 2017

Fig. 2.48: Distribution of the TID in ARC61 during the 2017 operation.

13.4 2018

Fig. 2.49: Distribution of the TID in ARC61 during the 2018 operation.

14 Comparison of the ARC BLM measurements with RPLs and NMOS dosimeters

Fig. 2.50: Boxplot representation of the ratios of TID measured by different radiation detectors, installed in ARCs' half-periods. Each box starts in the first quartile and ends in the third quartile. The upper (lower) whisker represents the last (first) data point that is within $1.5(\text{third_quartile} - \text{first_quartile})$ distance from the third (first) quartile.

As presented in Fig. 2.50 and Tab. 2.1, taking a BLM installed side of the beam line (approximately 30 cm from the beam) as a reference (dose in N_2), the median attenuation factor of the dose measured by the RPL (dose in SiO_2) installed at the cable try (approximately transversely 1 m from the beam, at the same longitudinal position) is 11.8 (with middle 50% of measurements in [7.7, 17.2] range). The median value ratio of the dose measured by the RPL, installed at the end of quadrupole (magnet coil), with respect to the side BLM (approximately the same distance from the beam) is 1.2 with 50% of measurements in the in [0.7, 1.8] range). Typically (median value) TIDs at the BI electronic racks (measured by the NMOS, approximately 4 m upstream of the side BLM) were 70 times lower, with 50% of measurements in the in [38, 189] range.

Table 2.1: Quarterlies of the ratios between TID measured by the different sensors (at different locations). Measurement from the different time periods are considered together. Q_n denotes the n'th quartile.

	RPL cable / side BLM	RPL coil / side BLM	RPL coil / bottom BLM	NMOS / side BLM
min	0.004	0.079	0.8	2.8E-04
Q_1	0.058	0.69	4.7	5.3E-03
Q_2	0.085	1.20	6.7	1.4E-02
Q_3	0.130	1.84	10.9	2.6E-02
max	0.419	15.3	319.0	6.5

Chapter 3

HEHeq fluence measurements in the SPS ring

Although this report focuses primarily on TID measurements, thanks to the upgrade of the RadMons in YETS 2016-2017, in both 2017 and 2018 High-Energy-Hadron-equivalent (HEH) fluence measurements were available. They are presented in Fig. 3.1 and Tab. E.1. In few locations (LSS1, LSS2) measurements did not cover the entire year, and therefore were extrapolated, assuming that their evolution over the injected intensity was constant.

Fig. 3.1: A High Energy Hadron equivalent fluence RadMon measurements in the years 2017 and 2018. Points were interconnected with line for visualisation purposes only, and due to point-wise nature of the measurements with relatively low granularity, HEH levels cannot be interpolated for the locations without the monitors.

Chapter 4

TID measurements in the selected Transfer Lines

This chapter covers TID measurement in the transfer lines related to the SPS – TT20/21/22 and TT40/41 (TT40 feeds LHC beam 2, through TI8, and AWAKE, through TT41). In the future update of the report, the measurements will be extended with the HiRadMat/LHC B1 extraction (TT60).

1 TT40 / TT41

Fig. 4.1: TID distribution in the transfer lines 40 and 41, measured by BLMs in the years 2015-2018. Point-like measurements were connected with lines for visualisation purposes only. [7]

Fig. 4.2: Evolution of the TID measured by the BLMs over time in years 2015-2018. This representation aims in indicating periods with no or suspicious logging as well as monthly changes in the loss distribution, and should not be used for retrieving the absolute TID. Measurements were normalised with the SPS injected intensity with the LHC or AWAKE as aimed destination. White regions correspond to periods without the data (problems with detector or detector not installed). [7]

2 TT20

Fig. 4.3: TID distribution in the transfer lines 20, 21, 22, and 24, measured by BLMs and RPLs in the years 2014-2015, 2016, and 2017-2018. Point-like measurements were connected with lines for visualisation purposes only.[7]

Fig. 4.4: Evolution of the TID measured by the BLMs over time in the transfer lines 20, 21, 22, and 24. This representation aims in indicating periods with no or suspicious logging as well as monthly changes in the loss distribution, and should not be used for retrieving the absolute TID. Measurements were normalised with the SPS **injected intensity** with the North Area as aimed destination. White regions correspond to periods without the data (problems with detector or detector not installed).[7]

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusions

Summary of the radiation levels along the SPS is depicted in Fig. 2.1. In LSS1, the annual measured TID levels (at the beam scraper (half-period 114) reached hundreds of kGy, whereas at the internal beam dump blocks (half-periods 117,118) measured levels were of up to few tens of kGy. In LSS2, that is the harshest area along the SPS in terms of radiation (due to slow extraction to North Area), the TID levels reached MGy levels per year (in the vicinity of septum magnets), as measured by both RPLs and BLMs. In the LSS3-6, the measured annual TID level were up to several kGy per year.

In the arc sections, levels at the BLM locations varied from few Gy, up to several kGy. In general, there is a good trend agreement, between measurements from the different radiation detectors.

There are certain half-periods (e.g. 205,231,235,305,413,613, 627-635) where the measured attenuation factors differ from global trends. Potential causes are: i) malfunctioning of the monitors, ii) uncommon radiation field map, due to iia) a peculiar shielding (e.g. corrector/bumper magnets, iib) a rare (in terms of arc sectors) dominating beam loss mechanism.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank HSE-RP-AS section, particularly Julia Brigitta Trummer, for providing RPL measurements used in this study; and Matteo Brucoli (BE-CEM-EPR) for the help in the RadMon data quality assessment.

References

- [1] Frederic Galleazzi. *SPS RING - SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION*. Tech. rep. SPSLM__0012 v.0 (EDMS id 972975). Oct. 2008. URL: <https://edms.cern.ch/document/972975/0>.
- [2] W. Scandale et al. “The UA9 setup for the double-crystal experiment in CERN-SPS”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 975 (2020), p. 164175. ISSN: 0168-9002. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2020.164175>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900220305714>.
- [3] Antonio Perillo-Marcone et al. “Analysis and Operational Feedback of the New High-Energy Beam Dump in the CERN SPS”. In: *9th International Particle Accelerator Conference*. 2018, WEPMG003. DOI: 10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2018-WEPMG003.
- [4] Didier Alberto et al. *HIGH-LEVEL DOSIMETRY RESULTS FOR THE CERN HIGH-ENERGY ACCELERATORS: Annual Report for 2014 and 2015*. CERN-RP-2016-086-REPORTS-TN (EDMS Id. 1685697). May 2016. URL: <https://edms.cern.ch/file/1685697/1/HLD14-15-PS-SPS.pdf>.
- [5] Matteo Brucoli. *Characterization of the NMOS DMN601 as Ionizing Radiation Dosimeter*. EDMS 1996667 v.1. June 2018. URL: <https://edms.cern.ch/document/1996667/1>.
- [6] Matteo Brucoli et al. *TID, Φ HEH and Φ ThN measurements along the SPS accelerator and the adjacent Tunnel Access Areas*. CERN-ACC-NOTE-2019-0043. July 2019. URL: <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2693061>.
- [7] Kacper Bilko. *Radiation levels in the TT20 TT40 TT41 transfer lines based on the BLM measurements in Run 2*. EDMS 2303449 v.1.1. May 2020. URL: <https://edms.cern.ch/document/2303449/1.1>.

Appendices A

BLM vs RPL measurements for years 2014-2015 and 2017-2018

1 2014-2015

Fig. A.1: Distribution of the TID in LSS1 during the 2014-2015 operation.

Fig. A.2: Distribution of the TID in LSS2 during the 2014-2015 operation.

Fig. A.3: Distribution of the TID in LSS3 during the 2014-2015 operation.

Fig. A.4: Distribution of the TID in LSS4 during the 2014-2015 operation.

Fig. A.5: Distribution of the TID in LSS5 during the 2014-2015 operation.

Fig. A.6: Distribution of the TID in LSS6 during the 2014-2015 operation.

Fig. A.7: Distribution of the TID in ARC12 during the 2014-2015 operation.

Fig. A.8: Distribution of the TID in **ARC23** during the **2014-2015** operation.

Fig. A.9: Distribution of the TID in **ARC34** during the **2014-2015** operation.

Fig. A.10: Distribution of the TID in **ARC45** during the **2014-2015** operation.

Fig. A.11: Distribution of the TID in **ARC56** during the **2014-2015** operation.

Fig. A.12: Distribution of the TID in **ARC61** during the **2014-2015** operation.

2 2017-2018

Fig. A.13: Distribution of the TID in **LSS1** during the **2017-2018** operation.

Fig. A.14: Distribution of the TID in LSS2 during the 2017-2018 operation.

Fig. A.15: Distribution of the TID in LSS3 during the 2017-2018 operation.

Fig. A.16: Distribution of the TID in LSS4 during the 2017-2018 operation.

Fig. A.17: Distribution of the TID in LSS5 during the 2017-2018 operation.

Fig. A.18: Distribution of the TID in LSS6 during the 2017-2018 operation.

Fig. A.19: Distribution of the TID in ARC12 during the 2017-2018 operation.

Fig. A.20: Distribution of the TID in **ARC23** during the **2017-2018** operation.

Fig. A.21: Distribution of the TID in **ARC34** during the **2017-2018** operation.

Fig. A.22: Distribution of the TID in **ARC45** during the **2017-2018** operation.

Fig. A.23: Distribution of the TID in **ARC56** during the **2017-2018** operation.

Fig. A.24: Distribution of the TID in **ARC61** during the **2017-2018** operation.

Appendices B

Injector Schedules

1 2014

ML

August 29, 2014
V1.7

2014 Injector Accelerator Schedule
Approved by the Research Board March 2014

Fig. B.1: Injector Schedule for 2014.

2 2015

Fig. B.2: Injector Schedule for 2015.

3 2016

ML

September 20, 2016

V2.1

2016 Injector Accelerator Schedule
Approved by the Research Board - September 2015

Fig. B.3: Injector Schedule for 2016.

4 2017

ML/RS

November 14, 2017
ver. 1.8

2017 Injector Accelerator Schedule
Approved by the Research Board, 8 March 2017

Fig. B.4: Injector Schedule for 2017.

5 2018

RS

June 6, 2018
ver. 1.6

Injector Accelerator Schedule 2018
Approved by Research board on 06.12.2017

Fig. B.5: Injector Schedule for 2018.

Appendices C

BLM annual measurements

Table C.1: Annual BLM TID measurements. BLMs with saturated signal are highlighted with red.

SPS.BLM.101	260.0	530.0	60.0	69.0	33.0
SPS.BLM.102	39.0	40.0	2.9	2.4	0.85
SPS.BLM.103	43.0	50.0	3.7	2.9	2.2
SPS.BLM.104	8.6	6.9	0.2	0.22	1.2
SPS.BLM.105	25.0	150.0	7.6	30.0	170.0
SPS.BLM.106	0.54	0.34	0.089	1.5	2.5
SPS.BLM.107	97.0	520.0	14.0	38.0	120.0
SPS.BLM.108	15.0	70.0	1.0	13.0	10.0
SPS.BLM.109	140.0	1300.0	72.0	950.0	54.0
SPS.BLM.110	8.4	160.0	6.5	320.0	1.6
SPS.BLM.111	26.0	200.0	24.0	460.0	14.0
SPS.BLM.112	31.0	100.0	30.0	44.0	31.0
SPS.BLM.113	67.0	290.0	36.0	160.0	39.0
SPS.BLM.114	45.0	820.0	16.0	620.0	110.0
SPS.BLM.115	1100.0	6100.0	3000.0	2800.0	8000.0
SPS.BLM.116	86.0	650.0	330.0	380.0	780.0
SPS.BLM.117	93.0	710.0	230.0	340.0	730.0
SPS.BLM.11732.MKDVI	1.0	40.0	5.9	37.0	6.0
SPS.BLM.11771	20.0	2900.0	1900.0	3700.0	6400.0
SPS.BLM.118	53.0	1500.0	1300.0	2300.0	2600.0
SPS.BLM.11809.QFA	200.0	4000.0	4100.0	6000.0	4400.0
SPS.BLM.11831.MDHD	32.0	1200.0	1100.0	1900.0	2300.0
SPS.BLM.11836	86.0	1500.0	840.0	1500.0	1800.0
SPS.BLM.11852.MSI	900.0	5900.0	3000.0	5600.0	12000.0
SPS.BLM.11872	400.0	5400.0	3000.0	7200.0	8100.0

Continued on next page

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
SPS.BLM.11904.MDVA	7400.0	57000.0	23000.0	33000.0	64000.0
SPS.BLM.11933.MKP1	550.0	5400.0	1500.0	3100.0	12000.0
SPS.BLM.11954.MKP4	160.0	2000.0	550.0	1300.0	1900.0
SPS.BLM.11998	120.0	440.0	640.0	470.0	670.0
SPS.BLM.120	74.0	310.0	340.0	360.0	450.0
SPS.BLM.121	810.0	7400.0	3500.0	3300.0	6200.0
SPS.BLM.122	25.0	500.0	130.0	410.0	300.0
SPS.BLM.123	520.0	4900.0	1800.0	2200.0	3500.0
SPS.BLM.124	31.0	270.0	140.0	190.0	260.0
SPS.BLM.125	150.0	1100.0	580.0	770.0	920.0
SPS.BLM.126	35.0	330.0	75.0	370.0	480.0
SPS.BLM.127	47.0	380.0	150.0	530.0	660.0
SPS.BLM.128	6.0	78.0	23.0	52.0	73.0
SPS.BLM.129	20.0	160.0	66.0	110.0	250.0
SPS.BLM.130	34.0	52.0	61.0	59.0	160.0
SPS.BLM.131	150.0	580.0	440.0	1100.0	2600.0
SPS.BLM.132	48.0	430.0	200.0	350.0	450.0
SPS.BLM.133	47.0	400.0	220.0	360.0	490.0
SPS.BLM.134	150.0	1500.0	1400.0	120.0	18.0
SPS.BLM.135	160.0	1600.0	1200.0	120.0	32.0
SPS.BLM.136	8.4	96.0	40.0	16.0	24.0
SPS.BLM.201	71.0	430.0	330.0	220.0	230.0
SPS.BLM.202	9.6	45.0	32.0	23.0	38.0
SPS.BLM.203	35.0	300.0	300.0	61.0	61.0
SPS.BLM.204	2.8	41.0	32.0	21.0	41.0
SPS.BLM.205	970.0	2500.0	3100.0	2900.0	13000.0
SPS.BLM.206	0.81	9.2	5.0	2.1	19.0
SPS.BLM.207	10.0	110.0	76.0	19.0	40.0
SPS.BLM.208	1.7	40.0	12.0	2.7	6.2
SPS.BLM.209	47.0	290.0	120.0	140.0	190.0

Continued on next page

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
SPS.BLM.210	15.0	13.0	6.2	24.0	27.0
SPS.BLM.211	120.0	280.0	340.0	270.0	470.0
SPS.BLM.212	17.0	42.0	49.0	5.1	67.0
SPS.BLM.213	21.0	86.0	110.0	49.0	260.0
SPS.BLM.214	26.0	290.0	510.0	650.0	2400.0
SPS.BLM.215	5.9	110.0	21.0	150.0	160.0
SPS.BLM.216	360.0	2300.0	190.0	1700.0	1200.0
SPS.BLM.21636.ZS1	24000.0	230000.0	65000.0	100000.0	120000.0
SPS.BLM.21652.ZS2	600.0	340000.0	170000.0	210000.0	260000.0
SPS.BLM.21658.ZS3	54000.0	360000.0	200000.0	270000.0	370000.0
SPS.BLM.21674.ZS4	60000.0	440000.0	200000.0	280000.0	330000.0
SPS.BLM.21680.ZS5	42000.0	280000.0	190000.0	240000.0	290000.0
SPS.BLM.21694.TCE	50000.0	360000.0	180000.0	220000.0	280000.0
SPS.BLM.217	7100.0	71000.0	25000.0	32000.0	38000.0
SPS.BLM.21772.TPST	11000.0	130000.0	140000.0	110000.0	96000.0
SPS.BLM.21775.MST1	9500.0	83000.0	84000.0	70000.0	78000.0
SPS.BLM.21776.MST1	8000.0	66000.0	68000.0	58000.0	74000.0
SPS.BLM.21792.MST3	6200.0	53000.0	59000.0	49000.0	51000.0
SPS.BLM.21796.MST3	6200.0	42000.0	44000.0	38000.0	39000.0
SPS.BLM.218	23000.0	140000.0	110000.0	9700.0	160000.0
SPS.BLM.21835.MSE1	1400.0	9500.0	7000.0	7100.0	9700.0
SPS.BLM.21839.MSE2	1100.0	7800.0	5700.0	6200.0	7500.0
SPS.BLM.219	1400.0	10000.0	6000.0	6800.0	9100.0
SPS.BLM.21905.QDA	7400.0	52000.0	33000.0	36000.0	56000.0
SPS.BLM.21931.OUT	1100.0	8300.0	4500.0	5000.0	9100.0
SPS.BLM.220	190.0	1500.0	720.0	880.0	1400.0
SPS.BLM.221	1800.0	14000.0	6100.0	8300.0	12000.0
SPS.BLM.222	46.0	290.0	170.0	320.0	340.0
SPS.BLM.223	200.0	1700.0	820.0	1500.0	1600.0
SPS.BLM.224	22.0	210.0	140.0	340.0	300.0

Continued on next page

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
SPS.BLM.225	180.0	1200.0	840.0	1100.0	1900.0
SPS.BLM.226	17.0	140.0	160.0	80.0	450.0
SPS.BLM.227	25.0	240.0	110.0	170.0	370.0
SPS.BLM.228	0.75	8.9	5.9	2.7	4.7
SPS.BLM.229	13.0	57.0	63.0	73.0	51.0
SPS.BLM.230	1.3	6.8	5.5	59.0	3.8
SPS.BLM.231	290.0	2300.0	1100.0	2400.0	5000.0
SPS.BLM.232	1.8	10.0	11.0	43.0	12.0
SPS.BLM.233	13.0	91.0	65.0	170.0	150.0
SPS.BLM.234	0.36	13.0	8.5	18.0	26.0
SPS.BLM.235	8.9	83.0	23.0	39.0	76.0
SPS.BLM.236	24.0	16.0	41.0	9.5	7.7
SPS.BLM.301	63.0	72.0	120.0	71.0	48.0
SPS.BLM.302	6.2	6.5	7.4	1.8	7.9
SPS.BLM.303	25.0	75.0	58.0	47.0	110.0
SPS.BLM.304	1.4	19.0	4.1	58.0	740.0
SPS.BLM.305	43.0	410.0	470.0	1700.0	2500.0
SPS.BLM.306	0.56	9.3	11.0	120.0	96.0
SPS.BLM.307	18.0	87.0	60.0	230.0	290.0
SPS.BLM.308	0.21	1.2	0.25	11.0	8.1
SPS.BLM.309	10.0	310.0	28.0	870.0	190.0
SPS.BLM.310	1.6	38.0	7.2	70.0	9.8
SPS.BLM.311	6.7	46.0	39.0	68.0	67.0
SPS.BLM.312	1.4	10.0	12.0	4.8	21.0
SPS.BLM.313	12.0	66.0	39.0	72.0	99.0
SPS.BLM.314	110.0	730.0	18.0	280.0	60.0
SPS.BLM.315	84.0	1500.0	12.0	99.0	19.0
SPS.BLM.316	15.0	180.0	7.1	7.7	6.4
SPS.BLM.317	16.0	290.0	2.5	3.4	6.5
SPS.BLM.318	0.5	20.0	0.96	0.56	3.2

Continued on next page

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
SPS.BLM.319	0.14	1.9	0.26	0.27	1.5
SPS.BLM.320	0.11	2.1	1.1	0.059	0.32
SPS.BLM.321	10.0	57.0	4.9	35.0	96.0
SPS.BLM.322	0.34	11.0	1.5	4.0	1.0
SPS.BLM.323	210.0	1300.0	550.0	850.0	1200.0
SPS.BLM.324	15.0	92.0	8.3	70.0	120.0
SPS.BLM.325	110.0	280.0	370.0	220.0	420.0
SPS.BLM.326	5.0	10.0	11.0	10.0	12.0
SPS.BLM.327	15.0	37.0	19.0	11.0	24.0
SPS.BLM.328	1.8	7.6	4.3	1.2	16.0
SPS.BLM.329	2.4	17.0	16.0	500.0	300.0
SPS.BLM.330	0.94	6.5	6.3	35.0	47.0
SPS.BLM.331	110.0	790.0	290.0	500.0	1100.0
SPS.BLM.332	18.0	97.0	68.0	100.0	520.0
SPS.BLM.333	20.0	76.0	160.0	90.0	680.0
SPS.BLM.334	0.55	5.5	18.0	8.4	19.0
SPS.BLM.335	4.2	7.4	14.0	10.0	42.0
SPS.BLM.336	5.7	6.9	7.2	24.0	39.0
SPS.BLM.401	62.0	270.0	300.0	320.0	500.0
SPS.BLM.402	20.0	110.0	72.0	100.0	100.0
SPS.BLM.403	14.0	78.0	73.0	93.0	87.0
SPS.BLM.404	0.83	18.0	8.3	18.0	19.0
SPS.BLM.405	14.0	110.0	90.0	100.0	220.0
SPS.BLM.406	0.037	0.75	0.94	4.0	6.2
SPS.BLM.407	4.3	6.4	7.8	19.0	180.0
SPS.BLM.408	3.8	5.3	7.4	11.0	45.0
SPS.BLM.409	31.0	270.0	240.0	380.0	210.0
SPS.BLM.410	0.77	3.3	3.3	3.0	4.0
SPS.BLM.411	21.0	120.0	94.0	120.0	440.0
SPS.BLM.412	1.4	12.0	5.7	9.0	32.0

Continued on next page

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
SPS.BLM.413	1.5	16.0	8.6	17.0	41.0
SPS.BLM.414	0.44	4.2	1.9	12.0	11.0
SPS.BLM.415	0.0024	4.6	0.43	31.0	0.91
SPS.BLM.416	3.4	41.0	5.6	93.0	21.0
SPS.BLM.417	6.1	21.0	27.0	44.0	120.0
SPS.BLM.418	20.0	39.0	44.0	90.0	56.0
SPS.BLM.41835.TPSG	2.6	51.0	30.0	130.0	37.0
SPS.BLM.41839.MSE1	0.7	15.0	6.6	28.0	10.0
SPS.BLM.41854.MSE2	0.47	12.0	5.4	25.0	11.0
SPS.BLM.41859.MSE3	0.27	11.0	5.2	20.0	7.0
SPS.BLM.41874.MSE4	0.017	9.4	4.0	19.0	7.4
SPS.BLM.41879.MSE5	0.011	6.5	2.6	15.0	4.7
SPS.BLM.41884.MSE6	0.022	8.6	3.6	16.0	5.4
SPS.BLM.41897	1.3	10.0	4.9	21.0	8.5
SPS.BLM.419	0.063	5.7	3.4	3.4	3.4
SPS.BLM.420	0.0077	3.6	2.9	4.4	9.7
SPS.BLM.421	0.14	4.9	5.9	130.0	23.0
SPS.BLM.422	0.0044	8.2	3.4	29.0	5.3
SPS.BLM.423	0.1	47.0	5.6	49.0	130.0
SPS.BLM.424	6.2	140.0	47.0	250.0	360.0
SPS.BLM.425	49.0	700.0	350.0	770.0	1400.0
SPS.BLM.426	48.0	430.0	260.0	440.0	450.0
SPS.BLM.427	43.0	330.0	190.0	310.0	330.0
SPS.BLM.428	9.0	42.0	23.0	23.0	35.0
SPS.BLM.429	17.0	150.0	80.0	88.0	150.0
SPS.BLM.430	1.8	13.0	11.0	4.4	8.0
SPS.BLM.431	16.0	170.0	34.0	56.0	97.0
SPS.BLM.432	0.54	17.0	12.0	7.9	3.8
SPS.BLM.433	13.0	81.0	88.0	84.0	120.0
SPS.BLM.434	5.0	25.0	21.0	13.0	42.0

Continued on next page

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
SPS.BLM.435	34.0	210.0	130.0	120.0	320.0
SPS.BLM.436	5.8	25.0	15.0	26.0	110.0
SPS.BLM.501	150.0	250.0	55.0	140.0	1400.0
SPS.BLM.502	26.0	36.0	4.3	12.0	310.0
SPS.BLM.503	32.0	64.0	11.0	13.0	210.0
SPS.BLM.504	3.4	4.6	2.4	1.4	23.0
SPS.BLM.505	10.0	30.0	16.0	28.0	170.0
SPS.BLM.506	0.42	0.98	0.76	2.3	15.0
SPS.BLM.507	5.3	22.0	13.0	37.0	100.0
SPS.BLM.508	2.8	8.1	5.4	34.0	61.0
SPS.BLM.509	100.0	280.0	250.0	120.0	180.0
SPS.BLM.510	3.3	4.9	5.1	2.9	4.0
SPS.BLM.511	65.0	180.0	70.0	140.0	150.0
SPS.BLM.512	13.0	46.0	11.0	91.0	61.0
SPS.BLM.513	120.0	440.0	220.0	290.0	230.0
SPS.BLM.514	39.0	140.0	62.0	85.0	93.0
SPS.BLM.515	15.0	130.0	27.0	290.0	390.0
SPS.BLM.516	5.9	48.0	6.3	38.0	74.0
SPS.BLM.51659	130.0	780.0	1.1	2.6	10.0
SPS.BLM.517	190.0	950.0	9.6	71.0	210.0
SPS.BLM.51760	12.0	88.0	3.3	4.7	26.0
SPS.BLM.51760.L	nan	nan	nan	nan	0.94
SPS.BLM.518	31.0	160.0	11.0	3.1	17.0
SPS.BLM.51899	5.0	17.0	3.8	2.0	4.1
SPS.BLM.519	3.2	20.0	5.5	0.89	3.3
SPS.BLM.520	1.0	12.0	7.2	10.0	27.0
SPS.BLM.521	2.7	26.0	36.0	110.0	630.0
SPS.BLM.52105	0.66	5.7	2.0	57.0	520.0
SPS.BLM.522	0.84	10.0	8.3	21.0	140.0
SPS.BLM.523	29.0	530.0	260.0	400.0	960.0

Continued on next page

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
SPS.BLM.524	2.8	46.0	36.0	110.0	60.0
SPS.BLM.525	130.0	650.0	370.0	660.0	680.0
SPS.BLM.526	4.7	17.0	7.9	57.0	9.4
SPS.BLM.527	7.1	25.0	13.0	84.0	20.0
SPS.BLM.528	3.6	12.0	2.3	4.4	99.0
SPS.BLM.529	4.5	24.0	29.0	300.0	160.0
SPS.BLM.530	0.11	0.95	0.57	78.0	0.95
SPS.BLM.531	10.0	93.0	12.0	600.0	3600.0
SPS.BLM.532	0.016	5.4	4.5	12.0	4.3
SPS.BLM.533	11.0	58.0	39.0	85.0	130.0
SPS.BLM.534	3.0	8.3	6.0	0.74	11.0
SPS.BLM.535	12.0	45.0	67.0	59.0	76.0
SPS.BLM.536	1.2	13.0	17.0	11.0	13.0
SPS.BLM.601	57.0	290.0	1000.0	660.0	2600.0
SPS.BLM.602	4.0	16.0	46.0	36.0	88.0
SPS.BLM.603	4.3	27.0	51.0	38.0	110.0
SPS.BLM.604	4.1	500.0	17.0	10.0	9.6
SPS.BLM.605	35.0	1300.0	59.0	54.0	550.0
SPS.BLM.606	5.5	62.0	31.0	18.0	100.0
SPS.BLM.607	6.6	81.0	49.0	32.0	94.0
SPS.BLM.608	3.4	25.0	7.9	15.0	8.5
SPS.BLM.609	26.0	200.0	110.0	390.0	110.0
SPS.BLM.610	5.8	53.0	27.0	110.0	19.0
SPS.BLM.611	9.3	140.0	65.0	120.0	51.0
SPS.BLM.612	3.5	48.0	21.0	19.0	24.0
SPS.BLM.613	6.1	48.0	30.0	45.0	39.0
SPS.BLM.614	11.0	55.0	54.0	390.0	140.0
SPS.BLM.615	4.0	130.0	27.0	110.0	39.0
SPS.BLM.616	2.6	97.0	17.0	98.0	34.0
SPS.BLM.61631.MKE1	0.4	38.0	1.8	60.0	17.0

Continued on next page

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
SPS.BLM.61634.MKE2	0.31	110.0	2.4	100.0	39.0
SPS.BLM.61637.MKE3	0.41	5.4	1.8	63.0	12.0
SPS.BLM.61651	0.29	0.85	1.2	56.0	6.2
SPS.BLM.617	12.0	19.0	47.0	110.0	15.0
SPS.BLM.61756	nan	nan	nan	nan	15.0
SPS.BLM.61771.QDA	8.4	100.0	68.0	290.0	91.0
SPS.BLM.61774.TPSG	15.0	210.0	150.0	430.0	160.0
SPS.BLM.61779.MST1	2.1	44.0	30.0	100.0	38.0
SPS.BLM.61794.MST2	0.8	30.0	20.0	48.0	25.0
SPS.BLM.618	9.8	38.0	26.0	66.0	43.0
SPS.BLM.61832.MSE1	1.8	16.0	13.0	38.0	22.0
SPS.BLM.61837.MSE2	2.7	11.0	9.7	28.0	15.0
SPS.BLM.61852.MSE3	1.2	8.6	8.7	20.0	11.0
SPS.BLM.61857.MSE4	3.5	7.3	6.2	13.0	13.0
SPS.BLM.61872.MSE5	2.4	10.0	9.6	26.0	15.0
SPS.BLM.619	0.37	1.6	0.88	1.0	0.95
SPS.BLM.620	0.042	1.3	0.78	0.89	0.46
SPS.BLM.621	170.0	230.0	990.0	1100.0	470.0
SPS.BLM.622	42.0	81.0	210.0	63.0	300.0
SPS.BLM.623	24.0	100.0	110.0	52.0	220.0
SPS.BLM.624	6.6	17.0	7.3	6.5	30.0
SPS.BLM.625	49.0	230.0	290.0	260.0	330.0
SPS.BLM.626	4.3	34.0	47.0	43.0	44.0
SPS.BLM.627	49.0	230.0	290.0	260.0	220.0
SPS.BLM.628	4.2	34.0	47.0	43.0	38.0
SPS.BLM.629	78.0	390.0	97.0	720.0	1200.0
SPS.BLM.630	26.0	31.0	6.1	39.0	98.0
SPS.BLM.631	79.0	390.0	96.0	720.0	1300.0
SPS.BLM.632	26.0	31.0	6.2	39.0	29.0
SPS.BLM.633	53.0	440.0	21.0	450.0	40.0

Continued on next page

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
SPS.BLM.634	72.0	830.0	7.8	510.0	43.0
SPS.BLM.635	18.0	280.0	82.0	210.0	73.0
SPS.BLM.636	0.98	21.0	12.0	15.0	15.0

Appendices D

Choice of BCT

```

1 is_not_empty = (lambda x: bcts[f'max_intensity_{x}'].notna())
2 threshold = 7e11
3 is_above_threshold = (lambda x: bcts[f'max_intensity_{x}'] > threshold)
4 _3 = is_not_empty(31832)
5 _4 = is_not_empty(41435)
6 _55 = is_not_empty(51895)
7 _57 = is_not_empty(51897)
8 _a57 = is_above_threshold(51897)
9 _a55 = is_above_threshold(51895)
10 _a3 = is_above_threshold(31832)
11 _a4 = is_above_threshold(41435)
12
13
14 bcts.loc[~_3 & ~_55 & ((~_4 ) | (_4 & _a57)), 'bcts'] = 51897
15 bcts.loc[~_3 & ((~_4 & _55) | (_4 & _a55)) , 'bcts'] = 51895
16
17 bcts.loc[_4 & ((_3 & ~_a3) | (~_3 & (~_a55 | (~_55 & (~_57 | ~_a57)) )), 'bcts'] = 41435
18 bcts.loc[_3 & (_a3 | ~_4), 'bcts'] = 31832

```

Listing D.1: Python code used to determine the Beam Current Transformer used in the intensity analysis for a given cycle.

Table D.1: Selection of the Beam Current Transformer (BCT) used for intensity analysis in a given cycle, depending on the data availability (empty cell means no data available) and measured maximum intensity over the cycle, where *th* is equal 7e11 charges. There were 4 BCTs available in the SPS: high-intensity one in the half-period 318, low-intensity in half-period 414, and two additional in LSS5.

max_intensity_31832	max_intensity_41435	max_intensity_51895	max_intensity_51897	bcts
<th		<th	<th	31832
<th		<th	>th	31832
<th		<th		31832
<th		>th	<th	31832
<th		>th	>th	31832
<th		>th		31832
<th			<th	31832
<th			>th	31832
<th				31832
>th	<th	<th	<th	31832
>th	<th	<th	>th	31832
>th	<th	<th		31832
>th	<th	>th	<th	31832
>th	<th	>th	>th	31832
>th	<th	>th		31832
>th	<th		<th	31832
>th	<th		>th	31832
>th	<th			31832
>th	>th	<th	<th	31832
>th	>th	<th	>th	31832
>th	>th	>th	<th	31832
>th	>th	>th	>th	31832
>th	>th	>th	>th	31832
>th	>th	>th	>th	31832

Continued on next page

max_intensity_31832	max_intensity_41435	max_intensity_51895	max_intensity_51897	bets
>th	>th		<th	31832
>th	>th		>th	31832
>th	>th			31832
>th		<th	<th	31832
>th		<th	>th	31832
>th		<th		31832
>th		>th	<th	31832
>th		>th	>th	31832
>th		>th		31832
>th			<th	31832
>th			>th	31832
>th				31832
<th	<th	<th	<th	41435
<th	<th	<th	>th	41435
<th	<th	<th		41435
<th	<th	>th	<th	41435
<th	<th	>th	>th	41435
<th	<th	>th		41435
<th	<th		<th	41435
<th	<th		>th	41435
<th	<th			41435
<th	>th	<th	<th	41435
<th	>th	<th	>th	41435
<th	>th	<th		41435
<th	>th	>th	<th	41435
<th	>th	>th	>th	41435
<th	>th	>th		41435
<th	>th		<th	41435
<th	>th		>th	41435
<th	>th			41435
	<th	<th	<th	41435
	<th	<th	>th	41435
	<th	<th		41435
	<th		<th	41435
	<th		>th	41435
	<th			41435
	>th	<th	<th	41435
	>th	<th	>th	41435
	>th	<th		41435
	>th		<th	41435
	>th		>th	41435
	>th			41435
	<th	>th	<th	51895
	<th	>th	>th	51895
	<th	>th		51895
	>th	>th	<th	51895
	>th	>th	>th	51895

Continued on next page

max_intensity_31832	max_intensity_41435	max_intensity_51895	max_intensity_51897	bets
	>th	>th		51895
		<th	<th	51895
		<th	>th	51895
		<th		51895
		>th	<th	51895
		>th	>th	51895
		>th		51895
			<th	51897
			>th	51897
				51897

Appendices E

RadMon Annual Measurements

Table E.1: Annual TID, HEH-eq and 1MeV-n-eq RadMon measurements in the years 2015-2018. Measurements denoted as *Strange* correspond to monitors whose time evolution wasn't physical (e.g. significant steps, missing data).

name	dcum	functional_element	variable	2015	2016	2017	2018
SIMA.1LI05S	65	10201	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	Readout 0	1.3E+09
			TID1_INT		0.9	TID below 100 mGy	0.3
SIMAD.1LI05S	65	10201	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		3.4E+12	Readout 0	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT		Strange	TID below 100 mGy	0.3
SIMA.1LI04S	193	10601	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	Readout 0	1.8E+09
			TID1_INT		Strange		0.7
SIMAD.1LI04S	193	10601	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		2.1E+12	Readout 0	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT		TID below 100 mGy	TID below 100 mGy	0.5
SIMA.1LI03S	379	11198	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	1.9E+09
			TID1_INT	3.1	1.7	TID below 100 mGy	0.6
SIMAD.1LI03S	379	11198	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Strange	Readout 0	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT	5.8	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	0.4
SIMAD.1LI02S	411	11297	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	2.0E+12	Readout 0	1.2E+10
			TID2_INT	20.7	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	6.8
SIMA.1LI02S	423	11338	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	1.7E+10
			TID1_INT	46.9	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	6.1
SIMAD.1LI01S	503	11580	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Strange	Readout 0	7.5E+11
			TID2_INT	50.8	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	Strange
SIMA.1LI01S	505	11593	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	1.8E+11
			TID1_INT	31.9	6.3	TID below 100 mGy	Strange
SIMA.1RI01S	551	11735	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	7.3E+10
			TID1_INT	37.9	14	TID below 100 mGy	24.1
SIMAD.1RI01S	551	11735	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Strange	Readout 0	5.2E+10
			TID2_INT	58.9	19.4	TID below 100 mGy	26.2
SIMA.1RI02S	685	12155	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	6.8E+10
			TID1_INT	40.8	15.2	TID below 100 mGy	14.4
SIMA.1RI03S	717	12255	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	No data in the last month
			TID1_INT	12.1	5.3	TID below 100 mGy	No data in the last month
SIMAD.1RI02S	729	12293	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	7.9E+11	Readout 0	7.5E+10
			TID2_INT	8.5	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	5.6
SIMAD.1RI03S	761	12393	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	1.0E+12	Readout 0	No data in the last month
			TID2_INT	16.6	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	No data in the last month
SIMA.1RI04S	961	13001	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	Readout 0	8.1E+10
			TID1_INT		5.8	TID below 100 mGy	16.6
SIMAD.1RI04S	961	13001	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Strange	Readout 0	1.8E+11
			TID2_INT		6.1	TID below 100 mGy	17.7

name	dcum	functional_element	variable	2015	2016	2017	2018
SIMA.1RI05S	1089	13401	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	Readout 0	9.1E+09
			TID1_INT		Strange	TID below 100 mGy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy
SIMAD.1RI05S	1089	13401	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		4.5E+12	Readout 0	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT		Strange	TID below 100 mGy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy
SIMA.2LI05S	1217	20201	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	5.6E+09	9.1E+09
			TID1_INT		1.8	1.4	1.7
SIMAD.2LI05S	1217	20201	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		1.5E+12	Readout 0	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT		1.9	1.6	2.1
SIMA.2LI04S	1345	20601	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	2.0E+09	6.8E+09
			TID1_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	0.8	1.9
SIMAD.2LI04S	1345	20601	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		2.5E+12	Readout 0	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	0.8	2.1
SIMA.2LI03S	1511	21138	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	4.2E+09	7.1E+09
			TID1_INT	TID below 100 mGy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	24.2	TID below 100 mGy
SIMAD.2LI03S	1531	21197	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	5.7E+11	1.0E+11	1.1E+11
			TID2_INT	7.9	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	0.9	4.5
SIMA.2LI02S	1595	21396	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	1.2E+10	2.1E+10
			TID1_INT	0.9	3.4	3.4	7
SIMAD.2LI02S	1595	21396	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Strange	1.7E+11	7.6E+10
			TID2_INT	3.1	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	2.8	6.1
SIMA.2LI01S	1653	21577	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	6.1E+10	4.7E+10
			TID1_INT	27.7	7.5	15.7	15.8
SIMAD.2LI01S	1653	21577	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	9.9E+11	8.1E+11	3.0E+11
			TID2_INT	39.8	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	12.1	14.9
SIMA.2RI01S	1830	22135	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	1.5E+11	No data in the last month
			TID1_INT	333.1	297.7	TID above 1 kGy	No data in the last month
SIMA.2RI04S	1854	22201	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	2.0E+11	No data in the last month
			TID1_INT		Strange	TID above 1 kGy	No data in the last month
SIMAD.2RI04S	1855	22401	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Strange	3.2E+12	No data in the last month
			TID2_INT		Strange	TID above 1 kGy	No data in the last month
SIMAD.2RI01S	1861	22233	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	4.1E+12	3.1E+12	No data in the last month
			TID2_INT	239.8	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID above 1 kGy	No data in the last month
SIMA.2RI02S	1863	22236	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	3.5E+11	No data in the last month
			TID1_INT	Strange	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	130	No data in the last month
SIMAD.2RI02S	1881	22293	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Strange	1.5E+12	No data in the last month
			TID2_INT	Strange	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	35.8	Strange
SIMA.2RI03S	1926	22434	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	6.4E+10	4.0E+10
			TID1_INT	19.2	13.2	13.3	13
SIMAD.2RI03S	1926	22434	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	7.2E+11	8.0E+11	3.3E+11
			TID2_INT	35.8	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	14.1	13.6
SIMA.2RI05S	2113	23001	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	4.5E+10	2.2E+10
			TID1_INT		Strange	8.7	5.1
SIMAD.2RI05S	2113	23001	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Negative Fluence	1.0E+11	3.1E+10
			TID2_INT		1.6	9.2	5.4
SIMA.2RI06S	2241	23401	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	2.5E+10	2.7E+10
			TID1_INT		TID below 100 mGy	TID below 100 mGy	TID below 100 mGy
SIMAD.2RI06S	2241	23401	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Negative Fluence	1.9E+11	9.4E+10

name	dcum	functional_element	variable	2015	2016	2017	2018
			TID2_INT		Strange	6.1	5.8
SIMA.3LI04S	2369	30201	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	2.8E+09	5.5E+09
			TID1_INT		Strange	Strange	Strange
SIMAD.3LI04S	2369	30201	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	Strange	Strange
			TID2_INT		Strange	Strange	Strange
SIMA.3LI03S	2497	30601	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	4.0E+10	3.2E+10
			TID1_INT		1.5	8.3	7.1
SIMAD.3LI03S	2497	30601	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	3.4E+11	2.5E+11
			TID2_INT		Strange	8.4	7.4
SIMA.3LI02S	2625	31001	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	3.2E+10	9.2E+09
			TID1_INT		Strange	7.9	Strange
SIMAD.3LI02S	2625	31001	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Strange	1.2E+11	3.6E+09
			TID2_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	5.9	Strange
SIMA.3LI01S	2753	31401	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	3.1E+10	6.4E+09
			TID1_INT		Strange	5.7	Strange
SIMAD.3LI01S	2753	31401	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	Strange	Strange
			TID2_INT		Strange	5.7	Strange
SIMA.3RI01S	2881	31801	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	7.8E+08	1.0E+09
			TID1_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	Strange	Strange
SIMAD.3RI01S	2881	31801	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Negative Fluence	Negative Fluence	Readout 0
			TID2_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	Strange	Strange
SIMA.3RI02S	3009	32201	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	3.3E+10	1.4E+10
			TID1_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	5.3	2.3
SIMAD.3RI02S	3009	32201	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	8.8E+10	Strange
			TID2_INT		Strange	6.1	2.3
SIMA.3RI03S	3137	32601	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	8.6E+09	6.5E+09
			TID1_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	1.8	1
SIMAD.3RI03S	3137	32601	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	Strange	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	1.6	1
SIMA.3RI04S	3265	33001	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	2.7E+10	2.3E+10
			TID1_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	3.3	2.8
SIMAD.3RI04S	3265	33001	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		4.8E+11	Negative Fluence	Strange
			TID2_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	2.8	2.7
SIMA.3RI05S	3393	33401	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	1.1E+09	5.1E+09
			TID1_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	0.9	1.8
SIMAD.3RI05S	3393	33401	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Negative Fluence	Strange	Strange
			TID2_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	0.7	1.6
SIMA.4LI05S	3521	40201	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	3.4E+10	2.8E+10
			TID1_INT		Strange	6.4	5.6
SIMAD.4LI05S	3521	40201	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	3.3E+11	2.0E+11
			TID2_INT		0.9	7.8	6.9
SIMA.4LI04S	3649	40601	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	8.5E+08	1.2E+09
			TID1_INT		760.2	0.8	0.8
SIMAD.4LI04S	3649	40601	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		3.5E+12	Readout 0	Readout 0
			TID2_INT		TID below 100 mGy	0.6	0.6
SIMA.4LI03S	3867	41297	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	1.9E+10	2.1E+09
			TID1_INT	TID below 100 mGy	847.5	Strange	0.5

name	dcum	functional_element	variable	2015	2016	2017	2018
SIMAD.4LI03S	3867	41297	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	9.9E+11	2.2E+11	1.3E+10
			TID2_INT	4.9	Strange	Strange	0.6
SIMA.4LI02S	3899	41397	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	3.9E+09	3.5E+09
			TID1_INT	TID below 100 mGy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy
SIMAD.4LI02S	3899	41397	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	3.2E+12	Strange	4.5E+10
			TID2_INT	2	Strange	Strange	0.9
SIMAD.4LI01S	3931	41497	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	2.7E+12	2.5E+11	1.1E+10
			TID2_INT	9	Strange	3.1	TID below 100 mGy
SIMA.4LI01S	3949	41555	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	2.0E+10	3.5E+09
			TID1_INT	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	Strange	8.4	1.9
SIMA.4RI01S	4068	41932	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	4.2E+09	2.4E+09
			TID1_INT	TID below 100 mGy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy
SIMAD.4RI01S	4068	41932	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0
			TID2_INT	3.7	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	Strange	Strange
SIMA.4RI02S	4109	42055	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	2.2E+10	1.3E+09
			TID1_INT	TID below 100 mGy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	Strange	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy
SIMAD.4RI02S	4109	42055	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Strange	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT	Strange	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	Strange	Strange
SIMA.4RI03S	4165	42233	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	8.0E+09	4.8E+09
			TID1_INT	TID below 100 mGy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	Strange
SIMAD.4RI03S	4165	42233	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Negative Fluence	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT	2.5	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	6.1	0.9
SIMA.4RI04S	4417	43001	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	1.2E+10	1.7E+10
			TID1_INT		TID above 1 kGy	1.3	4.1
SIMAD.4RI04S	4417	43001	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Negative Fluence	2.8E+10	Strange
			TID2_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	16.9	21.4
SIMA.4RI05S	4545	43401	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	1.2E+10	4.1E+10
			TID1_INT		TID below 100 mGy	TID below 100 mGy	TID below 100 mGy
SIMAD.4RI05S	4545	43401	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Negative Fluence	Strange	1.3E+11
			TID2_INT		TID below 100 mGy	TID below 100 mGy	TID below 100 mGy
SIMA.5LI04S	4673	50201	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	3.0E+09	6.2E+10
			TID1_INT		Strange	1.1	15
SIMAD.5LI04S	4673	50201	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		3.2E+11	Readout 0	6.1E+11
			TID2_INT		TID below 100 mGy	1	14.8
SIMA.5LI03S	4801	50601	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	1.0E+09	3.0E+09
			TID1_INT		Strange	0.6	0.5
SIMAD.5LI03S	4801	50601	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		4.3E+11	Readout 0	1.0E+10
			TID2_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	0.3	0.4
SIMA.5LI02S	4929	51001	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	7.9E+09	3.9E+09
			TID1_INT		1.9	3.5	1.3
SIMAD.5LI02S	4929	51001	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	7.9E+10	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT		Strange	3	1.3
SIMA.5LI01S	5057	51401	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	1.3E+10	1.1E+10
			TID1_INT		2	3.4	2
SIMAD.5LI01S	5057	51401	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Strange	2.4E+11	4.2E+10
			TID2_INT		1.7	3	2.1
SIMA.5RI01S	5185	51801	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	1.7E+09	2.5E+09

name	dcum	functional_element	variable	2015	2016	2017	2018
			TID1_INT		1.1	1.3	1
SIMAD.5RI01S	5185	51801	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Strange	Strange	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT		0.6	1.2	0.9
SIMA.5RI02S	5313	52201	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	3.4E+10	9.4E+10
			FLUENCE_B2_HEH_INT		Readout 0	6.0E+11	1.8E+11
			TID1_INT		Strange	8	23.8
SIMAD.5RI02S	5313	52201	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	Strange	6.2E+11
			TID2_INT		Strange	7.1	21.6
SIMA.5RI03S	5441	52601	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	2.2E+10	9.7E+09
			TID1_INT		Strange	5.3	2.2
SIMAD.5RI03S	5441	52601	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	Strange	Strange
			TID2_INT		Strange	4.7	2
SIMA.5RI04S	5569	53001	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	2.6E+10	7.0E+09
			TID1_INT		TID below 100 mGy	5.3	1.5
SIMAD.5RI04S	5569	53001	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	Negative Fluence	Negative Fluence
			TID2_INT		TID below 100 mGy	5	1.4
SIMA.5RI05S	5697	53401	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	3.3E+09	4.1E+09
			TID1_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	0.8	1
SIMAD.5RI05S	5697	53401	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0
			TID2_INT		Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	0.6	0.9
SIMA.6LI05S	5825	60201	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	1.7E+10	6.7E+10
			TID1_INT		0.7	3.7	18.2
SIMAD.6LI05S	5825	60201	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	1.7E+11	6.4E+11
			TID2_INT		1.5	4.4	21.9
SIMA.6LI04S	5953	60601	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	5.3E+09	4.3E+10
			TID1_INT		Strange	Strange	7.7
SIMAD.6LI04S	5953	60601	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		Readout 0	Negative Fluence	2.8E+11
			TID2_INT		TID above 1 kGy	Strange	8.9
SIMA.6LI03S	6139	61196	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	5.8E+09	5.3E+09
			TID1_INT	2.9	2	Strange	Strange
SIMAD.6LI03S	6139	61196	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Strange	Strange	6.4E+10
			TID2_INT	7.4	3.3	1	0.9
SIMA.6LI02S	6203	61396	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	4.5E+10	1.8E+10
			TID1_INT	Strange	1.5	9.2	3.7
SIMAD.6LI02S	6203	61396	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Strange	5.4E+11	2.1E+11
			TID2_INT	2.7	3	6.8	3.3
SIMA.6LI01S	6265	61592	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	1.7E+10	1.0E+10
			TID1_INT	1.7	1.3	3.2	2.5
SIMAD.6LI01S	6265	61592	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	2.6E+11	Strange	1.2E+11
			TID2_INT	7.4	Strange	2.1	1.9
SIMA.6RI01S	6371	61910	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	1.6E+09
			TID1_INT	Strange	1.8	TID below 100 mGy	Strange
SIMAD.6RI01S	6371	61910	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	Strange	Readout 0	6.4E+09
			TID2_INT	1.6	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	2.8
SIMA.6RI02S	6469	62232	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	2.2E+11
			TID1_INT	10.4	Strange	TID below 100 mGy	24.3
SIMAD.6RI02S	6469	62232	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	1.9E+12	Readout 0	6.1E+11

name	dcum	functional_element	variable	2015	2016	2017	2018
			TID2_INT	17.8	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	24
SIMA.6RI03S	6491	62296	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT	Readout 0	Readout 0	Readout 0	5.0E+10
			TID1_INT	2.3	5.6	TID below 100 mGy	7.3
SIMAD.6RI03S	6491	62296	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT	Readout 0	3.5E+11	Readout 0	1.5E+11
			TID2_INT	4.3	Negative TID below -0.1 Gy	TID below 100 mGy	5.8
SIMA.6RI04S	6721	63001	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	Readout 0	2.1E+10
			TID1_INT		TID above 1 kGy	TID below 100 mGy	31.2
SIMAD.6RI04S	6721	63001	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		5.5E+12	Readout 0	4.8E+10
			TID2_INT		TID above 1 kGy	TID below 100 mGy	28.3
SIMA.6RI05S	6849	63401	FLUENCE_B1_HEH_INT		Readout 0	Readout 0	2.1E+10
			TID1_INT		TID above 1 kGy	TID below 100 mGy	16.6
SIMAD.6RI05S	6849	63401	FLUENCE_1MEV_N_INT		5.5E+12	Readout 0	2.8E+10
			TID2_INT		TID above 1 kGy	TID below 100 mGy	17.9